

Certificate of Calibration

THERMOMETERS

17004E, 19206E, 19869E, 20399E

This certificate is issued in accordance with the laboratory accreditation requirements of the United Kingdom Accreditation Service. It provides traceability of measurement to the SI system of units and/or to units of measurement realised at the National Physical Laboratory or other recognised national metrology institutes. This certificate may not be reproduced other than in full, except with the prior written approval of the issuing laboratory.

FOR: Facility for Airborne Atmospheric Measurements
Building 146
Cranfield University
Cranfield
Bedfordshire
MK43 0AL

For the attention of Dr Hannah Price

DESCRIPTION: Four 50 Ω platinum resistance thermometers (PRTs)

IDENTIFICATION: Type: E102AL (Plate), E102AL (Plate), E102AL (Plate), E102AL (Loom)
Serial No: 17004E, 19206E, 19869E, 20399E

PREVIOUS CERTIFICATES: 17004E: Not previously calibrated at NPL
19206E: 2016010143 dated 2 February 2016
19869E: 2015110037-1 dated 10 December 2015
20399E: 2017050067 dated 22 May 2017

DATES OF CALIBRATION: 5 January to 11 January 2018

Reference: 2017120149-1

Date of issue: 17 January 2018

Checked by:

Signed:

Name: Dr S A Bell

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(Authorised Signatory)

on behalf of NPLML

This certificate is consistent with the capabilities that are included in Appendix C of the MRA drawn up by the CIPM. Under the MRA, all participating institutes recognise the validity of each other's calibration and measurement certificates for the quantities, ranges and measurement uncertainties specified in Appendix C (for details see <http://www.bipm.org>).

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MEASUREMENTS

As requested the platinum resistance thermometers (PRTs) were monitored using a precision resistance bridge with traceability to national standards, using an excitation current of 2.8 mA, and the resistance values obtained appear in the table below. At each generated condition a time of not less than 60 minutes was allowed for temperature to equilibrate. A set of 10 readings recorded at 1 minute intervals was then taken from the instruments under test.

The calibration was carried out in a test chamber, in air, against NPL reference thermometers. Traceability of measurement was provided by calibration of these thermometers to ITS-90 through NPL Temperature Standards.

The values of the applied conditions are shown in the first column of the table below. The values measured from the instruments under test are then quoted with their equivalent expanded uncertainties, shown in degrees Celsius. This quoted uncertainty relates to the period of the calibration and is not an indication of the long-term stability of the instruments.

The ambient conditions in the NPL humidity laboratory were $23\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 3\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and less than 80 % relative humidity.

Applied Condition	Test Thermometers				
Measured Temperature	Measured Resistance of PRT Serial Number 17004E	Measured Resistance of PRT Serial Number 19206E	Measured Resistance of PRT Serial Number 19869E	Measured Resistance of PRT Serial Number 20399E	Expanded Uncertainty of the Temperature Measurement
$^{\circ}\text{C}$	Ω	Ω	Ω	Ω	$^{\circ}\text{C}$
-60.05 #	38.184	38.198	38.200	37.977	± 0.10
-50.02 #	40.193	40.210	40.210	40.013	± 0.10
-40.01	42.194	42.211	42.209	42.038	± 0.08
-30.02	44.183	44.199	44.193	44.050	± 0.08
-19.98	46.159	46.189	46.181	46.066	± 0.08
-10.03	48.118	48.150	48.143	48.055	± 0.08
+0.02	50.091	50.127	50.117	50.059	± 0.05
+9.94	52.033	52.073	52.061	52.032	± 0.05
+19.99	53.998	54.038	54.024	54.025	± 0.05
+29.93	55.953	55.975	55.959	55.991	± 0.05
+39.91	57.872	57.912	57.893	57.958	± 0.05
+50.08	59.854	59.878	59.857	59.954	± 0.05

NOTE: # All points below $-40\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ are outside the range of UKAS accreditation of NPL for air temperature

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UNCERTAINTIES

The standard uncertainty of the applied condition represents a combination of the uncertainties arising from calibration and estimated stability of the reference standards, and from the method of transfer to the instrument under test.

The standard uncertainty of measurement is calculated by combining the uncertainty of the applied condition, the resolution of the instrument and its standard deviation for the period of the test. An uncertainty contribution has been included for rounding to give results an equivalent resolution of 0.01 °C.

The reported expanded uncertainty is based on a standard uncertainty multiplied by a coverage factor $k = 2$, providing a coverage probability of approximately 95 %. The uncertainty evaluation has been carried out in accordance with UKAS requirements.

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